

YUQORI DARAJALI TENGLAMALAR UCHUN KARDANO FORMULASI

Saliyeva Sevara Ma'mirbek qizi

Matematika va Informatika

kafedrasida o'qituvchisi,

Andijon davlat pedagogika instituti,

E-mail: saliyevasevara18@gmail.com,

Abdullayeva Madina Mamurjon qizi

Matematika va Informatika yo'nalishi talabasi,

Andijon davlat pedagogika instituti.

E-mail: abdullayevamadina0627@gmail.com.

Annotatsiya: Bu maqolada yuqori darajali kubik tenglamalarni yechish uchun Kardano usulidan foydalanish berilgan. Bu usul bilan kubik tenglamalarni yechish orqali iqtidorli o'quvchilarni matematika faniga bo'lgan qiziqishlarini ortirishga, ularni mustaqil ravishda bilim saviyalarini oshirishga va mantiqiy fikrlashiga yordam beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Viyet teoremasi, Bessel funksiyasi, kubik tenglama, Kardano, qo'shma kompleks sonlar.

Tenglamalar nazariyasi Bessel funksiyalarining nollari, integratsiya va boshqalar xarakteristik tenglamalarni o'rganishda zarur bo'lgan tenglamalarni yechishni o'rganamiz. Ko'phad yoki integral ratsional algebraik funksiya

$$y = a_0x^n + a_1x^{n-1} + a_2x^{n-2} \dots + a_n$$

ko'rinishda bo'ladi, bu yerda $a_0, a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n$ o'zgarmas koeffitsientlar, n esa ko'phadning darajasi va nomanfiy butun son.

$n = 1, 2, 3, 4$ bo'lganda mos chiziqli, kvadrat, kubik va bikvadrat funksiyalar deyiladi. O'zgarasni nol darajali ko'phad sifatida bilishimiz kerak.

Algebraik funksiya $P(x)y^n + P_1(x)y^{n-1} + P_2(x)y^{n-2} + \dots + P_n(x) = 0$

ko'rinishdagi tenglamani qanoatlantiruvchi xar qanday $y = f(x)$ funksiyadir. Bu yerda $P_0(x), P_1(x), P_2(x), \dots, P_n(x)$ lar o'zgaruvchining ko'phadlari deyiladi.

Algebraik tenglamalarda yechimlarini tenglamaning ildizlari (yoki nollari) sifatida ham qarash mumkin.

$ax + b = 0$ chiziqli tenglama uchun yechim $x = -\frac{b}{a}$, kvadrat tenglama uchun yechim

$x_{1,2} = \frac{-b \pm \sqrt{D}}{2a}$, kubik tenglamaning yechimlarini esa Kardano usulida topish mumkin.

Kubik tenglamani XI asrda Umar Xayyom (1048-1123) birinchi marta geometrik usulda ilk

bor hisoblagan. U uchinchi darajali tenglamani aylana va parabola tenglamalariga ajratib ularning kesishish nuqtasining berilgan tenglamaning yechimi ekanligini aniqlagan.

Italyan matematigi Djerolamo Kardano kubik tenglamani yechishning bu usulini 1545 yilda Ars Magna shahrida bayon qildi.

Kubik tenglamaning umumiy ko'rinishi

$$a_1x^3 + b_1x^2 + c_1x + d_1 = 0$$

(1)

Tenglamaning ikkala tomonini a_1 ga bo'lib $x^3 + bx^2 + cx + d = 0$

(2)

ko'rinishga keltiramiz.

Bu tenglamani $x = u - \frac{b}{3}$ (3) almashtirish

orqali soddaroq holga keltiramiz:

$$\left(u - \frac{b}{3}\right)^3 + b\left(u - \frac{b}{3}\right)^2 + c\left(u - \frac{b}{3}\right) + d = 0$$

$$\left(u^3 - 3u^2\frac{b}{3} + 3u\frac{b^2}{9} - \frac{b^3}{27}\right) + b\left(u^2 - 2u\frac{b}{3} + \frac{b^2}{9}\right) + c\left(u - \frac{b}{3}\right) + d = 0 \text{ yoki}$$

$$u^3 + pu + q = 0 \quad (4)$$

Bu yerda, $p = c - \frac{b^2}{u}, q = d - \frac{bc}{3} + \frac{2b^3}{27}$

(5)

Bu kubik tenglama uchun $u = y + z$ (6)

almashtirish olamiz.

$$(y + z)^3 = u^3$$

$$y^3 + 3y^2z + 3yz^2 + z^3 = u^3$$

$$y^3 + z^3 + 3yz(y + z) = u^3$$

$$u^3 - 3yzu - y^3 - z^3 = 0$$

(4) va (7) solishtirilib $p = -3yz, q = -(y^3 + z^3)$ ni belgilaymiz. Bu yerdan

$$yz = -\frac{p}{3} \quad \text{yoki} \quad y^3 z^3 = -\frac{p^3}{27}.$$

Demak $q = -(y^3 + z^3)$, $y^3 z^3 = -\frac{p^3}{27}$. Viyet teoremasiga ko'ra y^3, z^3 lar

$t^2 + qx - \frac{p^3}{27} = 0$ (8) kvadrat tenglamaning yechimi bo'la oladi. Shuning uchun

$$y^3 = \frac{-q + \sqrt{q^2 + 4\frac{p^3}{27}}}{2} = \frac{-q}{2} + \sqrt{\frac{q^2}{4} + \frac{p^3}{27}} \quad (9)$$

$$z^3 = \frac{-q - \sqrt{q^2 + 4\frac{p^3}{27}}}{2} = \frac{-q}{2} - \sqrt{\frac{q^2}{4} + \frac{p^3}{27}} \quad (10)$$

$\Delta = \frac{q^2}{4} + \frac{p^3}{27}$ belgilaymiz.

1-holat. Faraz qilaylik, $\Delta > 0$ bo'lsa, u holda y^3 va z^3 ikkalasi ham haqiqiy va (4) kubik tenglamaning ildizlari $y + z, \omega_1 y + \omega_2 z, \omega_2 y + \omega_1 z$ (12) ga teng bo'ladi. Bu yerda

$$\omega_1 = \frac{-1 + \sqrt{3}}{2} \quad \omega_2 = \frac{-1 - \sqrt{3}}{2} \quad \text{va} \quad (1, \omega_1, \omega_2)$$

ildizlari shundayki $1 + \omega_1 + \omega_2 = 0$

Demak (2) kubik tenglamaning izlanayotgan ildizlari quyidagiga teng bo'ladi.

$$\begin{cases} x_1 = u_1 - \frac{b}{3} = y + z - \frac{b}{3} \\ x_2 = u_2 - \frac{b}{3} = \omega_1 y + \omega_2 z - \frac{b}{3} \\ x_3 = u_3 - \frac{b}{3} = \omega_2 y + \omega_1 z - \frac{b}{3} \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

2-holat. Faraz qilaylik, $\Delta = 0$ bo'lsa, u holda y^3 va z^3 ikkalasi ham haqiqiy va (4) kubik tenglamaning ildizlari

$$y + z, \omega_1 y + \omega_2 z, \omega_2 y + \omega_1 z \quad \text{yoki} \quad 2y, -y, -y \quad (14)$$

ga teng. ($\omega_1 + \omega_2 = -1, y = z$).

Demak, (2) kubik tenglamaning izlanayotgan ildizlari quyidagiga teng.

$$\begin{cases} x_1 = 2y - \frac{b}{3} \\ x_2 = -y - \frac{b}{3} \\ x_3 = -y - \frac{b}{3} \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

3-holat. $\Delta < 0$ bo'lsa, u holda y^3 va z^3 ikkalasi ham kompleks sonlar va $y^3 = a + ib, z^3 = a - ib$ ga teng.

Agar kubik tenglamaning yechimlari $m + in$ va $m - in$ bo'lsa u holda (4) kubik

tenglamaning yechimlari quyidagiga teng bo'ladi.

$$\begin{cases} x_1 = y + z = m + in + m - in = 2m \\ x_2 = y\omega_1 + z\omega_2 = \omega_1(m + in) + \omega_2(m - in) = \\ x_3 = y\omega_2 + z\omega_1 = \omega_2(m + in) + \omega_1(m - in) = \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

Muavr formulasidan foydalanib bu yechimlarini quyidagicha ifodalash kerak. (4) Kubik tenglamaning yechimlari quyidagicha bo'ladi.

$$u = y + z = (a + ib)^{\frac{1}{3}} + (a - ib)^{\frac{1}{3}} + (a - ib)^{\frac{1}{3}} \quad (17)$$

$a = r \cos \varphi, b = r \sin \varphi, (r = \sqrt{a^2 + b^2}, \text{tg} \varphi = \frac{b}{a})$, lar o'rniga qo'yamiz

$$(a + ib)^{\frac{1}{3}} = (r(\cos \varphi - isin \varphi))^{\frac{1}{3}} = r^{\frac{1}{3}} \left(\cos \frac{\varphi + 2\pi k}{3} - isin \frac{\varphi + 2\pi k}{3} \right),$$

$$k = 0, 1, 2, \quad (19)$$

Shunday qilib (18), (19) larni (17) ga

$$\text{qo'yib } u = r^{\frac{1}{3}} \left(\cos \frac{\varphi + 2\pi k}{3} + isin \frac{\varphi + 2\pi k}{3} \right) + r^{\frac{1}{3}} \left(\cos \frac{\varphi + 2\pi k}{3} - isin \frac{\varphi + 2\pi k}{3} \right) = 2r^{\frac{1}{3}} \cos \frac{\varphi + 2\pi k}{3}$$

$$k = 0 \text{ da } 2r^{\frac{1}{3}} \cos \frac{\varphi}{3}, \quad k =$$

$$1 \text{ da } 2r^{\frac{1}{3}} \cos \frac{\varphi + 2\pi}{3}, \quad k =$$

$$2 \text{ da } 2r^{\frac{1}{3}} \cos \frac{\varphi + 4\pi}{3}$$

Natijada (2) kubik tenglamaning yechimlari

$$\begin{cases} x_1 = u_1 - \frac{b}{3} = 2r^{\frac{1}{3}} \cos \frac{\varphi}{3} - \frac{b}{3} \\ x_2 = u_2 - \frac{b}{3} = 2r^{\frac{1}{3}} \cos \frac{\varphi + 2\pi}{3} - \frac{b}{3} \\ x_3 = u_3 - \frac{b}{3} = 2r^{\frac{1}{3}} \cos \frac{\varphi + 4\pi}{3} - \frac{b}{3} \end{cases}$$

(13), (15), (20) sonlar kubik tenglama uchun **Kardano formulari** deyiladi.

Misol 1. Tenglamani yeching: $x^3 + 3x - 4 = 0$

Bu yerda Kardano formulasidan foydalanamiz: $x^3 + px + q = 0$

$$p = 3 \quad q = -4$$

$$y^3 = \frac{-q + \sqrt{q^2 + 4\frac{p^3}{27}}}{2} = \frac{-q}{2} + \sqrt{\frac{q^2}{4} + \frac{p^3}{27}} \quad (9)$$

$$y^3 = \frac{-q + \sqrt{q^2 + 4\frac{p^3}{27}}}{2} = \frac{-q}{2} + \sqrt{\frac{q^2}{4} + \frac{p^3}{27}}$$

$$= 2 + \sqrt{4 + 1} = 2 + \sqrt{5}$$

$$y = \sqrt[3]{2 + \sqrt{5}}$$

$$z^3 = \frac{-q - \sqrt{q^2 + 4\frac{p^3}{27}}}{2} = \frac{-q}{2} - \sqrt{\frac{q^2}{4} + \frac{p^3}{27}} \quad (10)$$

$$z^3 = \frac{-q + \sqrt{q^2 + 4\frac{p^3}{27}}}{2} = \frac{-q}{2} + \sqrt{\frac{q^2}{4} + \frac{p^3}{27}} = 2 - \sqrt{4 + 1} = 2 - \sqrt{5}$$

$$z = \sqrt[3]{2 - \sqrt{5}}$$

Kub ildiz ostidagi ifodalar uchun

$$2 + \sqrt{5} = \left(\frac{1 + \sqrt{5}}{2}\right)^3 \quad \text{va} \quad 2 - \sqrt{5} = \left(\frac{1 - \sqrt{5}}{2}\right)^3$$

Ekanligidan foydalansak, tenglamaning ildizlari hosil qilamiz:

$$x_1 = y + z = \frac{1 + \sqrt{5}}{2} + \frac{1 - \sqrt{5}}{2} = 1,$$

$$x_2 = y\omega_1 + z\omega_2 = \left(\frac{1 + \sqrt{5}}{2}\right) \left(\frac{-1 + \sqrt{3}}{2}\right) + \left(\frac{1 - \sqrt{5}}{2}\right) \left(\frac{-1 - \sqrt{3}}{2}\right) = -\frac{1}{2} + \frac{i\sqrt{15}}{2},$$

$$x_3 = y\omega_2 + z\omega_1 = \left(\frac{1 + \sqrt{5}}{2}\right) \left(\frac{-1 - \sqrt{3}}{2}\right) + \left(\frac{1 - \sqrt{5}}{2}\right) \left(\frac{-1 + \sqrt{3}}{2}\right) = -\frac{1}{2} - \frac{i\sqrt{15}}{2}.$$

Misol 2. Tenglamani yeching: $x^3 + 12x^2 + 45x + 54 = 0$

$$a = 1 \quad b = 12 \quad c = 45 \quad d = 54$$

$$x = u - \frac{b}{3} = u - \frac{12}{3} = u - 4 \quad (3)$$

almashtirish orqali soddaroq holga keltiramiz:

$$(u - 4)^3 + 12(u - 4)^2 + 45(u - 4) + 54 = 0$$

$$(u^3 - 12u^2 + 48u - 64) + 12(u^2 - 8u + 16) + 45(u - 4) + 54 = 0 \quad \text{yoki}$$

Tenglamani soddalashtirib

$$u^3 - 3u + 2 = 0 \quad (4)$$

Soddalashtirilgan misolni Kardano formulasiga qo'yishimiz mumkin.

$$\text{Demak, } u^3 - 3u + 2 = 0 \quad x^3 + px + q = 0$$

$$p = -3 \quad q = 2$$

$$y^3 = \frac{-q + \sqrt{q^2 + 4\frac{p^3}{27}}}{2} = \frac{-q}{2} + \sqrt{\frac{q^2}{4} + \frac{p^3}{27}} =$$

$$1 + \sqrt{1 + (-1)} = 1$$

$$y = \sqrt[3]{-1}$$

$$z^3 = \frac{-q - \sqrt{q^2 + 4\frac{p^3}{27}}}{2} = \frac{-q}{2} - \sqrt{\frac{q^2}{4} + \frac{p^3}{27}} = -1 -$$

$$\sqrt{1 + (-1)} = -1$$

$$z = \sqrt[3]{-1}$$

Ekanligidan foydalansak, tenglamaning ildizlari hosil qilamiz:

$$x_1 = y + z = -1 + (-1) = -2,$$

$$x_2 = y\omega_1 + z\omega_2$$

$$= (-1) \left(\frac{-1 + \sqrt{3}}{2}\right)$$

$$+ (-1) \left(\frac{-1 - \sqrt{3}}{2}\right) = 1$$

$$x_3 = y\omega_2 + z\omega_1$$

$$= (-1) \left(\frac{-1 - \sqrt{3}}{2}\right)$$

$$+ (-1) \left(\frac{-1 + \sqrt{3}}{2}\right) = 1$$

Turli matematika musobaqalari va olimpiadalarida kubik tenglamalariga bir necha bor duch kelamiz. Fan olimpiadalarida yuqori darajali tenglamalar bilan muammolar ko'p uchraydi. Bu tenglamalarni yechishda o'quvchilar ancha qiyinchiliklarga duch kelishlari mumkin. Bunday muammolarda Kardano usuli o'quvchilarga yengillik beradi. Kardano usuli o'quvchilardan mustaqil o'rganishni talab qiladi. O'quvchidan mustaqil o'rganish metodikasini shakllantiradi va shu bilan birga matematika faniga bo'lgan qiziqishini ortishiga sabab bo'ladi. Yuqorida keltirilgan kubik tenglamani yechishning Kardano usuli va uning isboti bunday qiyinchiliklarni yengishga yordam beradi.

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR

1. A. S. Yunusov, S. I. Afonina, M. A. Berdiqulov, D. I. Yunusova qiziqarli matematikava olimpiada masalalari. Toshkent, 2007
2. G.Gaymnazarov va boshq. Umar Xayyom va algebra //Fizika, matematika va informatika. 2014. № 5.– B.48-52.
3. Sh.A.Ayupov, B.A.Omirov, A.X.Xudoyberdiyev, F.H.Haydarov ALGEBRA VA SONLAR NAZARIYASI (o'quv qo'llanma).Toshkent, 2019
4. I.B.Kulanov Science and Innovation International Scientific Journal. 2022.№ 1.
5. Roman Witula, Damian Słota. Cardano's formula, square roots, Chebyshev polynomials and radicals. Journal of Mathematical Analysis and Applications.
6. To'ychiyev.Sh.Sh, & A. (2022 г.30-апрел). BA'ZI NOAN'ANAVIY MASALALARNING YECHIMLARI. *Eurasian Journal of Mathematical Theory and Computer Sciences*, сt: 65-68.
7. D. U. Madrahimov, T. S. (2022 г.9-сентябр). 6. D. U. Madrahimov, SUBSTANTIATION OF THE DIRECTION OF RESEARCH TO INCREASE THE PERFORMANCE OF LINTERS. 6. D. U. Madrahimov, T. S. (2022 г.9-сентябр). 2. D. U. MadrSUBSTANTIINNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGICA, 159-163 сtр.

